

LANGUAGE AND SOCIETY

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Annotation: this article discusses the relationship between language and society, the history of language, and its connection with human society. When talking about the interaction between language and society, it is necessary to dwell in detail on the concept of "society". There are many attempts and examples to interpret this concept.

Key words: sociology, society, language as a means of communication, social progress, main functions of language, language and culture, role of language in society.

Language is a sacred and honored concept, dear and honorable to every person like his mother. Language is a collection of unique sounds and symbols, each of which has a specific meaning. Language is an important means of human interaction and communication. Thanks to language, we can express our thoughts in the form of material speech. Language is not only a means of communication, but also a historical memory of every nation. In every language, the spiritual culture of every people, centuries-old history is expressed.

Sociolinguistics is the field that organizes relations between language and society, aspects of language related to philosophy, social psychology, ethnography. Sociolinguistics deals with the following issues:

- 1) society and language are interrelated, proportional historical process, phenomenon.
- 2) as the society progresses, the social functions of the language also improve.
- 3) the vocabulary of the literary language and dialects expands and increases.

4) the languages of people with close habitats, similar lifestyles and mutual economic relations influence each other. Languages are affected not only lexically, but also according to their grammatical aspects.

Just as a person's mind and consciousness appeared in the process of work, language also appeared in the process of people's work. At a certain period of human development, more precisely, during the primitive collective system, people had a desire to express their thoughts and feelings to each other during their work, and this prompted the emergence of the first simple language. Language and society are a phenomenon that affects each other, and one contributes to the development of the other.

The emergence and development of language is closely related to human society. Language is as old as the history of mankind. The development of language is inextricably linked with the development of society. It is known from the history of mankind that first the clan language was formed, then the language of the tribe, the language of the people, the people and the nation.

Language develops in society, its grammatical structure also improves. Language is a social phenomenon that forms communication between people in society. We need language only when there are people. So the language lives, develops and develops only in the society.

Therefore, language is a social phenomenon. The life of society is equal to the life of language. The language lives together with the society, and only the society receives the language.

An example of this is the following story: after a couple, whose main character is Tarzan, survives a shipwreck, their life continues in the jungle. There they have a child. However, the father died from an attack of monkeys, and the mother fell ill. A baby begins to be brought up as a "monkey" in the hands of monkeys. It is completely out of touch with human behavior and human "language". When he comes to people, he cannot get used to human life. He learns only three or four English words and runs away to the monkeys again...

In the family, the "language" of the child begins with hearing the "language" from the mother's heart. The first is the magical language - Mother Goddess!

Abdurauf Fitrat, who sacrificed his whole career for the freedom, development, and happiness of the nation, writes in his work "Rahbari Najot": «Just as the color of the water in the container is the same as the color of the water, so the children will accept any customs and morals of the environment in which they live. The greatest condition of moral education is that children receive more good and bad situations from their homes, friends on the street, and students at school».

Language is the most important communication tool of people. Language is the most important tool that helps people to communicate with each other. People express their thoughts and feelings through language. The role of language in the formation of human society is incomparable. After the emergence of language (this happened during the period of the primitive community system, according to scientists), society began to develop rapidly. There can be no society without language, no language without society, therefore language is a social phenomenon, that is, language does not belong to a single person, but to the whole society, and it is formed and developed with the help of members of this society. Only people organized as a society have a language as a means of communication. Language is a social phenomenon that has arisen on the basis of the historical and social experience of the human society over the centuries. Language and society development are inextricably linked. Any reality that occurs in society, in a certain sense, finds its expression in language. The social significance of language is manifested in its presence in society and serving the interests of society.

In conclusion, I will say that language is the main support of society, the primary means of human communication and relations, the soul of the nation and the destiny of statehood. The past, present and future of every people and nation, state and society, its existence is determined by the mother tongue. Language was created due to the need for communication, it means all the innovations and fruits of thought created by mankind in the process of communication, and it is passed down from generation to generation and preserved. After all, as long as there is a language, the nation is alive. The inextricable connection between language and society is a phenomenon that does not require proof. The interrelationship between language and society proves that both of them appeared at the same time, that language is one of the most important factors in society's becoming a society, and therefore, it is absolutely impossible to have a human society without language.

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